

THE ZAGREB INDICES AND SOME HAMILTONIAN PROPERTIES OF GRAPHS

Rao Li *

Dept. of Mathematical Sciences
University of South Carolina Aiken
Aiken, SC 29801
USA

Abstract

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. The first Zagreb index and second Zagreb index of G are defined as $\sum_{v \in V} d^2(v)$ and $\sum_{uv \in E} d(u)d(v)$, respectively. Using first and second Zagreb indices of graphs, we in this note present sufficient conditions for some Hamiltonian properties of graphs.

Keywords: The first Zagreb index, The second Zagreb index, Hamiltonian property

MSC: 05C09, 05C45

1. Introduction

We consider only finite undirected graphs without loops or multiple edges. Notation and terminology not defined here follow those in [2]. We use n and e to denote the number of vertices and edges of a graph, respectively. The complete graph of order n is denoted by K_n . We use G^c to denote the complement of a graph G . For a vertex v_i in a graph G , we use $d_i(G)$ to denote its degree in G . We use $\delta(G)$ to denote the minimum degree of G . We use $G \vee H$ to denote the the join of two disjoint graphs G and H . The first and second Zagreb indices were introduced by Gutman and Trinajstić in [3]. For a graph G , its first Zagreb index and second Zagreb index are defined as $Z_1(G) := \sum_{v \in V} d^2(v)$ and $Z_2(G) := \sum_{uv \in E} d(u)d(v)$, respectively. A cycle C in a graph G is called a Hamiltonian cycle of G if C contains all the vertices of G . A graph G is called Hamiltonian if G has a Hamiltonian cycle. A path P in a graph G is called a Hamiltonian path of G if P contains all the vertices of G . A graph G is called traceable if G has a Hamiltonian path.

In last several years, researchers have used different Zagreb indices to investigate the Hamiltonian properties of graphs (see [5], [1], [4]). In this note, we will present new sufficient conditions based upon the first and second Zagreb indices for the Hamiltonian and traceable graphs. The main results are as follows.

*E-mail address: raol@usca.edu Received: 24.05.2020 Accepted: 10.07.2020

Theorem 1. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 2$) graph of order n .

- 1) If $Z_1 \geq (n - k - 1)(n^2 + (k - 1)n - k^2 - 2k)$, then G is Hamiltonian or $K_k \vee K_{k+1}^c$.
- 2) If $Z_2 \geq (n - 1)(n - k - 1)(n^2 + (k - 1)n - 2k^2 - 3k)/2$, then G is Hamiltonian or $K_k \vee K_{k+1}^c$.

Theorem 2. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 1$) graph of order n .

- 1) If $Z_1 \geq (n - k - 2)(n^2 + kn - k^2 - 4k - 3)$, then G is traceable or $K_k \vee K_{k+2}^c$.
- 2) If $Z_2 \geq (n - 1)(n - k - 2)(n^2 + kn - 2k^2 - 7k - 5)/2$, then G is traceable or $K_k \vee K_{k+2}^c$.

2. Proofs

Proof of Theorem 1. Let G be a graph satisfying the conditions in Theorem 1. Suppose that G is not Hamiltonian. Then G is not a complete graph. We further have that $n \geq 2k + 1$ otherwise $2\delta \geq 2k \geq n$ and G is Hamiltonian. Since $k \geq 2$, G contains a cycle. Choose a longest cycle C in G and give an orientation on C . Since G is not Hamiltonian, there exists a vertex $x_0 \in V(G) - V(C)$. By Menger's theorem, we can find s ($s \geq k$) pairwise disjoint (except for x_0) paths P_1, P_2, \dots, P_s between x_0 and $V(C)$. Let u_i be the end vertex of P_i on C , where $1 \leq i \leq s$. We use u_i^+ to denote the successor of u_i along the orientation of C , where $1 \leq i \leq s$. Then $\{x_0, u_1^+, u_2^+, \dots, u_s^+\}$ is independent otherwise G would have cycles which are longer than C . Therefore $S := \{x_0, u_1^+, u_2^+, \dots, u_k^+\}$ is independent. Set $T := V(G) - S = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_r\}$. Thus $|T| = r = n - |S| = n - (k + 1) \geq k$.

Proof of 1). From the definition of Z_1 , we have

$$\begin{aligned} (n - k - 1)(n^2 + (k - 1)n - k^2 - 2k) &\leq Z_1 = \sum_{v \in V} d^2(v) \\ &= d^2(x_0) + d^2(u_1^+) + \dots + d^2(u_k^+) + d^2(v_1) + \dots + d^2(v_r) \\ &\leq (k + 1)r^2 + r(n - 1)^2 = (n - k - 1)(n^2 + (k - 1)n - k^2 - 2k). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $d(x_0) = d(u_1^+) = \dots = d(u_k^+) = r = n - (k + 1)$ and $d(v_1) = \dots = d(v_r) = d(v_{n-(k+1)}) = n - 1$. Now G is $K_r \vee K_{k+1}^c = K_{n-(k+1)} \vee K_{k+1}^c$. It is obvious that G is Hamiltonian if $r = n - (k + 1) \geq (k + 1)$. So it is impossible that $r \geq (k + 1)$. Thus $r = n - (k + 1) = k$. Therefore G is $K_k \vee K_{k+1}^c$.

Proof of 2). From the definition of Z_2 , we have

$$\begin{aligned} (n - 1)(n - k - 1)(n^2 + (k - 1)n - 2k^2 - 3k)/2 &\leq Z_2 \\ &= \sum_{uv \in E} d(u)d(v) = \sum_{u \in S, v \in T, uv \in E} d(u)d(v) + \sum_{u \in T, v \in T, uv \in E} d(u)d(v) \\ &\leq \sum_{u \in S, v \in T} d(u)d(v) + \sum_{u \in T, v \in T, u \neq v} d(u)d(v) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq r(n-1)(k+1)r + (n-1)(n-1)r(r-1)/2 \\ &= (n-1)(n-k-1)(n^2 + (k-1)n - 2k^2 - 3k)/2. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $d(x_0) = d(u_1^+) = \dots = d(u_k^+) = r = n - (k + 1)$ and $d(v_1) = \dots = d(v_r) = d(v_{n-(k+1)}) = n - 1$. Now G is $K_r \vee K_{k+1}^c = K_{n-(k+1)} \vee K_{k+1}^c$. It is obvious that G is Hamiltonian if $r = n - (k + 1) \geq (k + 1)$. So it is impossible that $r \geq (k + 1)$. Thus $r = n - (k + 1) = k$. Therefore G is $K_k \vee K_{k+1}^c$.

This completes the proof of Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 2. Let G be a graph satisfying the conditions in Theorem 2. Suppose that G is not traceable. Then G is not a complete graph. We further have that $n \geq 2k + 2$ otherwise $2\delta \geq 2k \geq n - 1$ and G is traceable. Choose a longest path P in G and give an orientation on P . Let y and z be the two end vertices of P . Since G is not traceable, there exists a vertex $x_0 \in V(G) \setminus V(P)$. By Menger's theorem, we can find s ($s \geq k$) pairwise disjoint (except for x_0) paths P_1, P_2, \dots, P_s between x_0 and $V(P)$. Let u_i be the end vertex of P_i on P , where $1 \leq i \leq s$. Since P is a longest path in G , $y \neq u_i$ and $z \neq u_i$, for each i with $1 \leq i \leq s$, otherwise G would have paths which are longer than P . We use u_i^+ to denote the successor of u_i along the orientation of P , where $1 \leq i \leq s$. Then $\{x_0, y, u_1^+, u_2^+, \dots, u_s^+\}$ is independent otherwise G would have paths which are longer than P . Therefore $S := \{x_0, y, u_1^+, u_2^+, \dots, u_k^+\}$ is independent. Set $T := V(G) - S = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_r\}$. Thus $|T| = r = n - |S| = n - (k + 2) \geq k$.

Proof of 1). From the definition of Z_1 , we have

$$\begin{aligned} (n-k-2)(n^2 + kn - k^2 - 4k - 3) &\leq Z_1 = \sum_{v \in V} d^2(v) \\ &= d^2(x_0) + d^2(y) + d^2(u_1^+) + \dots + d^2(u_k^+) + d^2(v_1) + \dots + d^2(v_r) \\ &\leq (k+2)r^2 + r(n-1)^2 = (n-k-2)(n^2 + kn - k^2 - 4k - 3). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $d(x_0) = d(y) = d(u_1^+) = \dots = d(u_k^+) = r = n - (k + 2)$ and $d(v_1) = \dots = d(v_r) = d(v_{n-(k+2)}) = n - 1$. Now G is $K_r \vee K_{k+2}^c = K_{n-(k+2)} \vee K_{k+2}^c$. It is obvious that G is traceable if $r = n - (k + 2) \geq (k + 1)$. So it is impossible that $r \geq (k + 1)$. Thus $r = n - (k + 2) = k$. Therefore G is $K_k \vee K_{k+2}^c$.

Proof of 2). From the definition of Z_2 , we have

$$\begin{aligned} (n-1)(n-k-2)(n^2 + kn - 2k^2 - 7k - 5)/2 &\leq Z_2 \\ &= \sum_{uv \in E} d(u)d(v) = \sum_{u \in S, v \in T, uv \in E} d(u)d(v) + \sum_{u \in T, v \in T, uv \in E} d(u)d(v) \\ &\leq \sum_{u \in S, v \in T} d(u)d(v) + \sum_{u \in T, v \in T, u \neq v} d(u)d(v) \\ &\leq r(n-1)(k+2)r + (n-1)(n-1)r(r-1)/2 \\ &= (n-1)(n-k-2)(n^2 + kn - 2k^2 - 7k - 5)/2. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $d(x_0) = d(y) = d(u_1^+) = \dots = d(u_k^+) = r = n - (k + 2)$ and $d(v_1) = \dots = d(v_r) = d(v_{n-(k+2)}) = n - 1$. Now G is $K_r \vee K_{k+2}^c = K_{n-(k+2)} \vee K_{k+2}^c$. It is obvious that G is traceable if $r = n - (k + 2) \geq (k + 1)$. So it is impossible that $r \geq (k + 1)$. Thus $r = n - (k + 2) = k$. Therefore G is $K_k \vee K_{k+2}^c$.

This completes the proof of Theorem 2.

References

- [1] M. An and K. Das, First Zagreb index, k -connectivity, β -deficiency and k -Hamiltonicity of graphs, *MATCH Commun. Math. Comput. Chem.* 80 (2018) 141 – 151.
- [2] J. A. Bondy and U. S. R. Murty, Graph Theory with Applications, Macmillan, London and Elsevier, New York (1976).
- [3] I. Gutman and N. Trinajstić, Graph theory and molecular orbitals, total π -electron energy of alternant hydrocarbons, *Chem. Phys. Lett.* 17 (1972) 535 – 538.
- [4] R. Li, The hyper-Zagreb index and some Hamiltonian properties of graphs, *Discrete Math. Lett.* 1 (2019) 54 – 58.
- [5] R. Li and M. Taylor, The first Zagreb index and some Hamiltonian properties of the line graph of a graph, *Journal of Discrete Mathematical Sciences and Cryptography* 20 (2017) 445 – 451.